

Water depletion and $^{15}\text{NH}_3$ in the atmosphere of the coldest brown dwarf observed with JWST/MIRI

H. Kühnle¹, P. Patapis¹, P. Mollière², P. Tremblin³, E. Matthews², A. M. Glauser¹, N. Whiteford⁴, M. Vasist⁵, O. Absil⁵, D. Barrado⁶, M. Min⁷, P.-O. Lagage⁸, L. B. F. M. Waters^{7,9}, M. Guedel^{10,2,1}, Th. Henning¹², B. Vandenbussche¹¹, P. Baudoz¹², L. Decin¹¹, J. P. Pye¹³, P. Royer¹¹, E. F. van Dishoeck¹⁴, G. Östlin¹⁵, T. P. Ray¹⁶, and G. Wright¹⁷

(Affiliations can be found after the references)

ABSTRACT

Context. With a temperature of ~ 285 K WISEJ0855–0714 (hereafter WISE 0855) is the coldest brown dwarf observed so far. Such cold gas giants enable probing atmospheric physics and chemistry of evolved objects similar to the Solar System gas giants.

Aims. Using the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) we obtained observations that allow us to characterize WISE 0855's atmosphere focusing on vertical variation in the water steam abundance, measuring trace gas abundances and receiving bulk parameters for this cold object.

Methods. We observed the ultra cool dwarf WISE 0855 using the Mid-Infrared Instrument Medium Resolution Spectrometer (MIRI/MRS) onboard JWST at a spectral resolution of up to $3^{\circ}750$. We combined the observation with the published data from the Near Infrared Spectrograph (NIRSpec) G395M and PRISM modes yielding a spectrum ranging from 0.8 to 22 μm . We applied atmospheric retrievals using `petitRADTRANS` to measure atmospheric abundances, the pressure-temperature structure, radius and gravity of the brown dwarf. We also employed publicly available clear and cloudy self-consistent grid models to estimate bulk properties of the atmosphere such as the effective temperature, radius, gravity and metallicity.

Results. Atmospheric retrievals constrain a variable water abundance profile in the atmosphere, as predicted by equilibrium chemistry. We detect the $^{15}\text{NH}_3$ isotopolog and infer a ratio of volume fraction of $^{14}\text{NH}_3/^{15}\text{NH}_3 = 349^{+53}_{-41}$ for the clear retrieval. We measure the bolometric luminosity by integrating the presented spectrum and obtain a value of $\log(L/L_{\odot}) = -7.291 \pm 0.008$.

Conclusions. The detected water depletion indicates that water condenses out in the upper atmosphere due to the very low effective temperature of WISE 0855. The height in the atmosphere where this occurs is covered by the MIRI/MRS data, and thus demonstrates the potential of MIRI to characterize cold gas giant's atmospheres. Comparing the data to retrievals and self-consistent grid models, we do not detect signs for water ice clouds, although their spectral features have been predicted in previous studies.

Key words. Stars: brown dwarfs, atmospheres – Planets and satellites: atmospheres – Instrumentation: spectrographs – Methods: observational

Appendices (available only online)

References

- Lacy, B. & Burrows, A. 2023, ApJ, 950, 8
Leggett, S. K., Tremblin, P., Phillips, M. W., et al. 2021, ApJ, 918
Meisner, A. M., Leggett, S. K., Logsdon, S. E., et al. 2023, AJ, 166, 57
Mukherjee, S., Fortney, J. J., Morley, C. V., et al. 2024, ApJ, 963, 73
-
- ¹ ETH Zürich, Institute for Particle Physics and Astrophysics, Wolfgang-Pauli-Str. 27, 8093 Zürich, Switzerland
² Max-Planck-Institut für Astronomie, Königstuhl 17, D-69117 Heidelberg, Germany
³ Université Paris-Saclay, UVSQ, CNRS, CEA, Maison de la Simulation, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France.
⁴ Department of Astrophysics, American Museum of Natural History, New York, NY 10024, USA
⁵ STAR Institute, Université de Liège, Allée du Six Août 19c, 4000 Liège, Belgium
⁶ Centro de Astrobiología (CAB), CSIC-INTA, ESAC Campus, Camino Bajo del Castillo s/n, 28692 Villanueva de la Cañada, Madrid, Spain
⁷ SRON Netherlands Institute for Space Research, Niels Bohrweg 4, 2333 CA Leiden, The Netherlands
⁸ Université Paris-Saclay, Université Paris Cité, CEA, CNRS, AIM, F-91191 Gif-sur-Yvette, France
⁹ Department of Astrophysics/IMAPP, Radboud University, PO Box 9010, 6500 GL Nijmegen, The Netherlands
¹⁰ Department of Astrophysics, University of Vienna, Türkenschanzstr. 17, 1180 Vienna, Austria
¹¹ Institute of Astronomy, KU Leuven, Celestijnenlaan 200D, 3001 Heverlee, Belgium
¹² LESIA, Observatoire de Paris, Université PSL, CNRS, Sorbonne Université, Université de Paris Cité, 5 place Jules Janssen, 92195 Meudon, France
¹³ School of Physics & Astronomy, Space Park Leicester, University of Leicester, 92 Corporation Road, Leicester, LE4 5SP, UK
¹⁴ Leiden Observatory, Leiden University, P.O. Box 9513, 2300 RA Leiden, The Netherlands
¹⁵ Department of Astronomy, Oskar Klein Centre, Stockholm University, 106 91 Stockholm, Sweden
¹⁶ School of Cosmic Physics, Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies, 31 Fitzwilliam Place, Dublin, D02 XF86, Ireland
¹⁷ UK Astronomy Technology Centre, Royal Observatory Edinburgh, Blackford Hill, Edinburgh EH9 3HJ, UK

Appendix A: Data quality and error inflation

In this section we want to include additional information on the error inflation on the presented data set shown in Figure A.1 and the signal to noise ratio presented in Figure A.2.

Appendix B: Atmospheric retrievals

The following Figures present additional material on the atmospheric retrievals performed on the data set. We show the opacities used in Figure B.1, present the calculated and constrained values for the three retrievals as well as the priors in Table B.1. The corresponding corner plots for the bulk parameter and gas abundances are shown in Figure B.2 and for the cloud and abundance profile related parameter given in Figure B.3. The comparison of the resulting evidence for the retrievals is shown in Table B.2.

Appendix C: Self-consistent grid models

This section includes additional grid model fits from the models by Lacy & Burrows (2023) and the Sonora Elf Owl fit by Mukherjee et al. (2024). The comparison between the four cloudy models of Lacy & Burrows (2023) with either equilibrium or non-equilibrium and thick or thin clouds is presented in Figure C.1. The best-fits of Sonora Elf Owl and the clear and equilibrium model by (Lacy & Burrows 2023) are compared in Figure C.2. Further, the comparison how χ^2 changes with the dependence of the wavelength as well as the reduced χ^2 per model is presented in Figure C.3. An overall model comparison between the fitted values is presented in Figure C.4 and the corresponding values are listed in Table C.1. The latter includes the fit parameter for either fitting only for the mid-infrared and setting a lower boundary to the gravity estimate. The calculated luminosities for each best-fit model is presented in Table C.2.

Fig. A.1. The upper plot shows the data with the uncertainty either estimated from the empirical error shown in red error bars and with the error inflation factor in blue error bars. The lower plot shows the error estimated from the pipeline, the empirical error and the final error with the included error inflation factor plotted along the wavelength. The inflation factor used here is $b = -7.78$.

Fig. A.2. The signal to noise ratio (SNR) for the error of the pipeline in green, the empirical error in red and the empirical error with the inflation factor in blue. The lower plot shows an inset of the upper plot scaled in the y-axis to better visualize the SNR of the empirical error with the inflation factor. The latter data are the data used in the analysis.

Fig. B.1. The upper plot shows the log opacities of methane, water, carbon monoxide, ammonia and phosphine for the retrieval analysis. The lower plot shows the ratio between the opacity of ¹⁵NH₃ and NH₃ as a function of wavelength showing where we would expect changes in the opacity due to the isotopologue. The opacities were taken at the temperature of $T_{\text{eff}} = 277$ K and a pressure of 1.02 bar according to the effective temperature estimate of the retrieval and the corresponding PT profile.

Table B.1. Retrieval results of the three presented retrievals.

Variable	Prior	Retrieval clear const. H ₂ O		Retrieval clear var. H ₂ O		Retrieval cloudy var. H ₂ O	
		Posterior	Best Fit	Posterior	Best Fit	Posterior	Best Fit
Radius [R_J]	$\mathcal{U}(0.489, 2.934)$	0.840 ^{+0.008} _{-0.008}	0.847	0.822 ^{+0.011} _{-0.012}	0.806	0.834 ^{+0.005} _{-0.005}	0.834
log(g) [cm/s ²]	$\mathcal{U}(2.0, 6.0)$	4.68 ^{+0.06} _{-0.06}	4.65	4.70 ^{+0.06} _{-0.06}	4.73	4.93 ^{+0.04} _{-0.05}	4.97
M [M_J]	-	13.00 ^{+1.95} _{-1.63}	12.93	13.71 ^{+1.87} _{-1.62}	14.04	23.73 ^{+2.48} _{-2.65}	26.57
T_{eff} [K]	-	296.9 ^{+1.4} _{-1.5}	297.7	300.3 ^{+2.1} _{-2.0}	304.7	297.0 ^{+1.1} _{-1.1}	298.9
log(H ₂ O)	$\mathcal{U}(-9.999999, -0.000001)$	-3.24 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	-3.26	-3.12 ^{+0.07} _{-0.05}	-3.01	-3.07 ^{+0.02} _{-0.02}	-3.07
log(CO ₂)	$\mathcal{U}(-9.999999, -0.000001)$	-9.10 ^{+0.11} _{-0.14}	-9.16	-8.91 ^{+0.12} _{-0.13}	-8.70	-8.72 ^{+0.06} _{-0.06}	-8.67
log(CO)	$\mathcal{U}(-9.999999, -0.000001)$	-6.85 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	-6.87	-6.71 ^{+0.08} _{-0.07}	-6.61	-6.74 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	-6.74
log(CH ₄)	$\mathcal{U}(-9.999999, -0.000001)$	-3.37 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	-3.41	-3.26 ^{+0.07} _{-0.05}	-3.17	-3.12 ^{+0.02} _{-0.02}	-3.12
log(NH ₃)	$\mathcal{U}(-9.999999, -0.000001)$	-4.29 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	-4.33	-4.25 ^{+0.04} _{-0.04}	-4.20	-4.22 ^{+0.02} _{-0.02}	-4.22
log(PH ₃)	$\mathcal{U}(-9.999999, -0.000001)$	-8.15 ^{+0.11} _{-0.13}	-8.11	-7.95 ^{+0.13} _{-0.13}	-7.92	-9.94 ^{+0.62} _{-0.65}	-10.77
log(H ₂ S)	$\mathcal{U}(-9.999999, -0.000001)$	-4.74 ^{+0.11} _{-0.13}	-4.71	-4.62 ^{+0.11} _{-0.12}	-4.59	-4.63 ^{+0.11} _{-0.15}	-4.54
log(¹⁵ NH ₃)	$\mathcal{U}(-9.999999, -0.000001)$	-6.85 ^{+0.14} _{-0.17}	-6.89	-6.79 ^{+0.13} _{-0.15}	-6.81	-6.76 ^{+0.08} _{-0.09}	-6.75
γ	$\mathcal{U}(0.000000, 9999953948)$	2.9e-7 ^{+0.5} _{-0.4}	3.0e-7	3.6e-7 ^{+0.7} _{-0.6}	3.7e-7	5.3e-7 ^{+0.6} _{-0.5}	5.5e-7
log(pbase _{H₂O})	$\mathcal{U}(-5.999999, 3.999999)$	-	-	-0.46 ^{+0.30} _{-0.16}	-0.10	-0.30 ^{+0.08} _{-0.08}	-0.30
alpha _{H₂O}	$\mathcal{U}(-0.999999, 7.999999)$	-	-	2.62 ^{+2.95} _{-1.44}	0.69	2.80 ^{+1.12} _{-0.78}	3.03
f _{sed}	$\mathcal{U}(1.000001, 10.999999)$	-	-	-	-	4.57 ^{+1.10} _{-0.92}	4.66
log(K _{zz}) [cm ² /s]	$\mathcal{U}(0.000001, 9.999999)$	-	-	-	-	1.7 ^{+0.4} _{-0.5}	2.0
log(σ_{Inorm})	$\mathcal{U}(1.01, 2.96)$	-	-	-	-	1.81 ^{+0.55} _{-0.45}	1.35
b _{MIRI}	$\mathcal{U}(-13.400955, -5.638476)$	-7.71 ^{+0.02} _{-0.02}	-7.71	-7.73 ^{+0.02} _{-0.02}	-7.73	-7.76 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	-7.75
b _{G395M}	$\mathcal{U}(-18.697953, -7.392405)$	-8.77 ^{+0.03} _{-0.02}	-8.76	-8.75 ^{+0.03} _{-0.03}	-8.72	-8.79 ^{+0.02} _{-0.02}	-8.79
b _{PRISM1}	$\mathcal{U}(-19.618027, -8.789751)$	-13.45 ^{+0.07} _{-0.07}	-13.42	-13.66 ^{+0.13} _{-0.19}	-13.86	-14.07 ^{+0.05} _{-0.05}	-14.12
b _{PRISM2}	$\mathcal{U}(-20.736958, -12.267634)$	-9.55 ^{+0.08} _{-0.08}	-9.62	-9.48 ^{+0.07} _{-0.07}	-9.47	-9.89 ^{+0.06} _{-0.06}	-9.97
log(H ₂ O(c))	$\mathcal{U}(-9.999999, -0.000001)$	-	-	-	-	-4.33 ^{+0.21} _{-0.16}	-4.36
log(pbase _{H₂O(c)})	$\mathcal{U}(-5.0, 2.0)$	-	-	-	-	1.05 ^{+0.02} _{-0.02}	1.03

Note: We compare the posterior distribution results to the posteriors, the best fit values and show the uniformly sampled priors used for the setup. The posterior values correspond to the median values on the posterior distribution and the uncertainty estimates on the difference between the median and the 16th and 84th percentile correspondingly. For gas molecules we report logarithmic volume fractions. The abundance of the cloud molecule H₂O(c) is given in logarithmic mass fraction.

Fig. B.2. Posterior distributions of the retrieval outputs for the Radius (R_{pl}) in R_J , the surface gravity ($\log(g)$) in dex and the logarithmic mass fractions of the following molecules: H_2O , CO_2 , CO , CH_4 , NH_3 , PH_3 , H_2S and $^{15}\text{NH}_3$. In blue we show the results from the cloudy, variable water profile retrieval, in red the distributions from the clear and variable water profile and in orange the values of the clear and constant water profile retrieval. The black lines correspond to the mean values for the cloudy retrieval.

Table B.2. The nested sampling global logarithmic evidence for the presented atmospheric retrievals.

Model	$\ln(Z)$
Ret. clear, const. H_2O	20468.45 ± 0.29
Ret. clear, var. H_2O	20482.80 ± 0.30
Ret. cloudy, const. H_2O .	20585.19 ± 0.31
Ret. cloudy, var. H_2O	20616.73 ± 0.32
Ret. clear, const. H_2O , no $^{15}\text{NH}_3$	20458.56 ± 0.29

Fig. B.3. The posterior distributions for the cloud parameter. On the upper reversed plot, we show the following variables for the cloudy with variable water profile retrieval: The logarithmic pressure for the cloud base ($\log_Pbase_H2O(c)$), the logarithmic cloud particle mass fraction ($\log_X_cb_H2O(c)$), the width of the cloud particle distribution ($sigma_inorm$), the logarithmic eddy diffusion coefficient (log_kzz), the sedimentation parameter and cloud thickness indicator (f_sed), the amount by which the liquid water in the atmosphere is reduced by the variable water profile ($alpha_H2O$), the pressure value where to reduce the amount of liquid water ($pbase_H2O$). The lower plot compares the two values for the variable water profile (pressure and amount of change in abundance) for the two retrievals with variable water profiles: In blue we show the distribution for the cloudy and in red for the clear retrieval. The values noted on top of each distribution correspond to the median and the 16th and 84th percentile correspondingly. The solid lines correspond to the mean values of the cloudy and the red lines to the ones of the clear retrieval with variable water profile.

Fig. C.1. Comparing the cloudy models both with and without equilibrium chemistry and two different thicknesses of water clouds by Lacy & Burrows (2023). The best fit models in the cloudy case using the the equilibrium thin and thick and the disequilibrium self-consistent thin and thick grid models by Lacy & Burrows (2023). The corresponding reduced χ^2 values are 2.48, 1.97, 3.48 and 2.75 for the equilibrium thin, thick and disequilibrium thin and thick cloudy models. As for the other models, we re-binned the models and data to a resolution $R = 500$ for NIRSspec/G395M and MIRI/MRS and NIRSspec/PRISM is kept at $R = 100$.

Fig. C.2. Comparing the best-fit equilibrium chemistry clear model by Lacy & Burrows (2023) with the clear disequilibrium model Sonora Elf Owl by Mukherjee et al. (2024). The corresponding reduced χ^2 is 12.72 for the Lacy model and 6.77 for Sonora Elf Owl. Again, for better visibility the presented models and data are re-binned to a resolution $R = 500$ for the NIRSpc/G395M and MIRI/MRS and NIRSpc/PRISM is kept at $R = 100$.

Fig. C.3. The left plots compare the χ^2 values for the different self-consistent models for each part of the spectrum. The right plots show the overall reduced χ^2 for each model. The upper plots show all models and the lower plot show an inset region marked in gray. The Lacy Cloudy NEQ (thick) model reaches the lowest χ^2 values over all. The ATMO++ model fits similarly well especially in the mid infrared. We use the values of the 10^b from the clear and variable water profile retrieval for the χ^2 calculation.

Fig. C.4. Comparing the model value outputs of the self-consistent grid model ATMO++ (Leggett et al. 2021; Meisner et al. 2023), Lacy & Burrows (2023) and Sonora Elf Owl Mukherjee et al. (2024) from top to bottom: The effective temperature T_{eff} , the logarithmic surface gravity $\log(g)$, the radius of the gas giant, the calculated mass based on the radius and the surface gravity, the metallicity $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ with 0 solar values and ± 0.5 super and sub-solar values correspondingly, the logarithmic luminosity compared to solar and the χ^2 of the fit. Filled circles correspond to cloudy models and the colors correspond to the same as shown in Figures ??, C.1 and C.2. Errors of the estimated values are too small to be depicted. The dotted lines correspond to the median value of the eight shown model spectra and in the legend the median and the standard error are presented.

Table C.1. Summary of the fitted parameters of the self-consistent grid models: ATMO++, Lacy & Burrow and Sonora Elf Owl.

Model	T_{eff} [K]	$\log(g)$ [cm/s^2]	R_{pl} [$\times R_J$]	Mass [$\times M_J$]	[M/H] [#]
ATMO ++ no PH_3	297.4 ± 0.7	4.167 ± 0.008	0.789 ± 0.006	3.6809 ± 0.0003	0
Lacy eq. clear	261.4 ± 0.6	3.501 ± 0.001	0.940 ± 0.009	1.1300 ± 0.0004	$0.499 \pm <0.001$
Lacy eq. cloudy (thick)	$250.0 \pm <0.1$	$3.500 \pm <0.001$	1.281 ± 0.009	2.0966 ± 0.0007	-0.386 ± 0.002
Lacy eq. cloudy (thin)	250.8 ± 0.2	3.501 ± 0.001	1.251 ± 0.008	2.0037 ± 0.0006	-0.215 ± 0.002
Lacy non-eq. clear	250.0 ± 0.1	$3.500 \pm <0.001$	1.147 ± 0.008	1.6803 ± 0.0005	0.491 ± 0.003
Lacy non-eq. cloudy (thick)	248.4 ± 0.5	$3.500 \pm <0.001$	1.304 ± 0.011	2.1693 ± 0.0007	-0.447 ± 0.004
Lacy non-eq. cloudy (thin)	240.0 ± 0.5	$3.500 \pm <0.001$	1.395 ± 0.011	2.4826 ± 0.0008	-0.305 ± 0.004
Sonora Elf Owl	$275.0 \pm <0.1$	$3.230 \pm <0.001$	0.975 ± 0.003	0.3252 ± 0.0004	0.406 ± 0.005
<i>Ignore NIRSpec/PRISM and phot.</i>					
ATMO ++ no PH_3	309.0 ± 0.6	4.094 ± 0.008	0.742 ± 0.006	2.7582 ± 0.0002	0
Lacy eq. clear	256.5 ± 0.6	$3.501 \pm <0.001$	1.002 ± 0.009	1.2839 ± 0.0004	$0.499 \pm <0.001$
Lacy eq. cloudy (thick)	284.1 ± 5.3	$4.000 \pm <0.001$	1.376 ± 0.260	7.6418 ± 0.0011	-0.127 ± 0.002
Lacy eq. cloudy (thin)	293.6 ± 1.1	3.745 ± 0.008	0.899 ± 0.013	1.8144 ± 0.0003	-0.057 ± 0.003
Lacy non-eq. clear	278.4 ± 0.2	$3.500 \pm <0.001$	0.933 ± 0.006	1.1127 ± 0.0004	$0.500 \pm <0.001$
Lacy non-eq. cloudy (thick)	274.9 ± 0.2	3.710 ± 0.025	1.068 ± 0.007	2.3598 ± 0.0005	-0.288 ± 0.022
Lacy non-eq. cloudy (thin)	274.3 ± 0.6	3.594 ± 0.004	1.058 ± 0.008	1.7734 ± 0.0005	-0.168 ± 0.004
Sonora Elf Owl	306.9 ± 1.2	3.745 ± 0.006	0.810 ± 0.009	1.4706 ± 0.0003	0.738 ± 0.005
<i>Constrain $\log(g)$ to 4.0 - 5.0</i>					
ATMO ++ no PH_3	297.4 ± 0.6	4.166 ± 0.008	0.789 ± 0.006	3.6823 ± 0.0003	0
Lacy eq. clear	260.7 ± 0.6	$4.001 \pm <0.001$	0.941 ± 0.008	3.5800 ± 0.0004	$0.500 \pm <0.001$
Lacy eq. cloudy (thick)	227.9 ± 0.2	$4.000 \pm <0.001$	1.539 ± 0.011	9.5625 ± 0.0010	-0.180 ± 0.005
Lacy eq. cloudy (thin)	226.9 ± 0.2	$4.000 \pm <0.001$	1.494 ± 0.011	9.0093 ± 0.0009	-0.055 ± 0.005
Lacy non-eq. clear	242.6 ± 0.4	4.248 ± 0.002	1.251 ± 0.010	11.1709 ± 0.0006	0.481 ± 0.003
Lacy non-eq. cloudy (thick)	229.2 ± 0.2	$4.000 \pm <0.001$	1.541 ± 0.011	9.5840 ± 0.0010	-0.185 ± 0.002
Lacy non-eq. cloudy (thin)	225.9 ± 0.1	$4.000 \pm <0.001$	1.576 ± 0.011	10.0277 ± 0.0010	-0.072 ± 0.002
Sonora Elf Owl	$275.0 \pm <0.1$	$4.000 \pm <0.001$	0.765 ± 0.005	2.3616 ± 0.0002	0.169 ± 0.007

Note: We use solar metallicity models for ATMO++.

Table C.2. The luminosity of the best-fit models calculated by integrating the flux from 0.45 to 30 μm .

Model	L/L_{\odot} [#]
ATMO++ no PH_3	-7.318
Lacy eq. clear	-7.458
Lacy eq. cloudy (thick)	-7.280
Lacy eq. cloudy (thin)	-7.294
Lacy non-eq. clear	-7.336
Lacy non-eq. cloudy (thick)	-7.271
Lacy non-eq. cloudy (thin)	-7.271
Median	-7.294 ± 0.023

Note: We do not calculate the Sonora Elf Owl model as the models only cover up to 15 μm .